

Evaluating the Challenges Faced by Tertiary Institutions in Providing Inclusive Education: *Results from one Private University in the Southern East region of Botswana*

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Abstract

The concept of inclusive education is based on the principle that all children regardless of their learning ability, race and gender, to mention but a few, have a basic right to be educated alongside their peers in inclusive schools. This study examined the challenges faced by tertiary institutions when providing inclusive education in the context of Botswana. Data were collected through the use of; interviews, focus groups, observation and document analysis. 39 participants were randomly selected for data collection in one of the private universities located in the Southern East region of Botswana. Data were analysed using the Thematic Analysis approach. The findings of the study revealed that the special needs students and lecturers at tertiary education encountered some challenges when implementing inclusive education curriculum due to limited teaching and learning resources. As a result, the study recommended that tertiary education regulatory bodies have to ensure that tertiary institutions in Botswana support inclusive education by providing the required teaching and learning resources. The study further recommended that: Lecturers should be trained on special and inclusive education; institutions should provide adequate teaching and learning resources as well conducive infrastructure in order to implement successful inclusive education

Keywords: *Challenges of Inclusive Education: Lecturer: Learner: Learning Disability: Special Education: Student, Teaching And Learning Resources: Tertiary Institutions*

Introduction

Inclusive education approaches maintain that special needs students ought to share the same classroom with students without learning disabilities. According to the African Disability Rights (2015), inclusive education needs to address and respond to the diverse needs of all kinds of students in any given educational setting. This implies that inclusive education should be inculcated in the schools' cultures and the societies at large and this could be accomplished through the provision of teaching and learning pedagogy that meets the needs of all learners (African Disability Rights, 2015). Similarly, Mitchel (2015) concurred with the African Disability Rights by stating that when a teaching and learning pedagogy which accommodates all learners' needs is provided, such strategy would enhance equality in the development of the economy in general. On the other hand, Save the Children Report (2016) describes inclusive education as a measure which is motivated by the desire to have a rights-based quality education and places more emphasis on inclusiveness in terms of education accessibility, participation and meeting individual learning needs towards building students' competencies. An inclusive learning environment is that which promotes complete equal treatment of all learners regardless of their learning abilities towards the provision of quality education to all. This, therefore, involves the modification and the transformation of learning content, methods, structures and policies; with a collective view to include all kinds of learners by education systems across the globe (Jonas, 2014). However, there are several challenges that make the provision of inclusive education a challenging experience; for example, most of the tertiary institutions in Botswana are still struggling with the implementation of inclusive education to the level of national educational policies (Molosiwa & Malope, 2011).

Based on this background, this study investigated on the challenges faced by tertiary institutions in Botswana towards the provision of inclusive education.

Statement of the Problem

Most of the students with special needs face some challenges when they progress to tertiary education because most of the tertiary institutions in Botswana do not effectively accommodate such students. Research shows that several institutions of higher learning are not fully equipped with the resources that enable them to provide satisfactory inclusive education. According to Jonas (2013) the introduction of inclusive education in public schools in Botswana, exposed teachers to new challenges in discharging their normal duties, especially the teaching of slow and fast learners with various disabilities. Research shows that Botswana has various forms of disabilities, ranging from handicapped learners, the academically challenged, visually or hearing impaired students as well as other forms of learning disabilities (Mukhopadhyay et al., 2017).

Despite the various dimensions of inclusive education, its sole purpose is to provide all learners equal opportunity to learn by sharing the same classroom with those without learning disabilities. However, studies indicate that the special learners themselves, tutors and learners without learning disabilities are not comfortable with being in the same learning environment with special needs students. Though inclusive education has been considered as a possible practice (Mpofu, 2007), the fact that lecturers and learners without learning disabilities display negative attitudes towards learners with disabilities, inclusive education is surrounded with several challenges during its implementation. Therefore, this study was conducted in one of the private institutions located in the Southern East region of Botswana and was based in the special needs unit to investigate on the challenges faced by lecturers and students during the implementation of inclusive education.

Research Objectives

The study was driven by the following objectives:

1. To explore the challenges faced by tertiary institutions when providing inclusive education in Botswana.
2. To identify challenges faced by students with learning disabilities in their learning environment.
3. To determine solutions that can reduce challenges faced by tertiary institutions when providing inclusive education in Botswana.

Research Questions

This study addressed the following research questions:

1. What are the challenges faced by tertiary institutions when providing inclusive education in Botswana?
2. What are the challenges faced by students with learning disabilities in their learning environment?
3. What are the solutions to challenges faced by tertiary institutions when providing inclusive education in Botswana?

Significance of the Study

The findings of this study may help the policy makers such as Botswana Qualifications Authority (BQA) to promote inclusive education in Botswana especially in institutions of higher education. This may also be extended to the health policy makers for them to effectively enforce standards and policies that promote safe and healthy learning environments that protect special needs students. The findings may further assist tertiary institutions to bridge the gaps identified by this study for effective delivery and facilitation of the special needs unit and total inclusion of learners with special needs. This study also adds to the body of knowledge in this area of study.

Literature Review

In this chapter, the researchers explored the challenges of inclusive education implementation experienced across the globe. Good (1959) cited in Singh (2016), stated that literature review is very important in that it awards the researcher an opportunity to find significant data on similar studies.

Understanding Inclusive Education

UNESCO (2019) highlighted that inclusive education is concerned with ensuring that each and every learner has equal opportunity to education regardless of their ability or disability. In other words, inclusive education seeks to promote full participation of learners regardless of their learning abilities. The National Academics Press (2019) pointed out that the importance of inclusive classrooms is to promote the concept that students of all backgrounds should have equal access to teaching and learning resources, and this ideology has been held by many countries recently. Countries such as; Botswana, South Africa, Zimbabwe, India, China and many others continue to make efforts in ensuring that their education systems infuse and implement inclusive education at all levels. A report by the Open Society Foundation (2019) highlighted that the successful integration of inclusive education in higher education creates beneficial teaching and learning environments which lead to high academic performance among learners.

A similar study conducted by Nestbit (2015) indicated that learners with disabilities demonstrated high academic achievement when they learned simultaneously with their counterparts in the same environment. This then implies that students with similar values of cultures, most often create amongst themselves, a sense of belonging regardless of their learning differences resulting in high levels of self-esteem. Nestbit (2015) in his study established that learners who originated from the same village or culture are likely to promote unity and a sense of belonging towards supporting each other. In support of this context is McLeod (2018), when he stated in his study that the Maslow's hierarchy of needs uphold that students of similar groups find it easier to make friends, trust and accept each other regardless of their various learning abilities.

In this paper, inclusive education is perceived as a pedagogical approach that responds to the various needs of all learners by increasing their participation in educational classroom activities and practices as posited by (Molosiwa & Mangope, 2011). In Botswana, the literature about inclusive education initiatives shows that, many learners with diverse forms of disabilities are being absorbed in the general education system. However, research points out that the special needs learners' contribution in the core academic curriculum is not fully possible when they are taught in separate classrooms. All the teaching and learning resources therefore need to be made available to all learners without segregating them based on their learning abilities (Government of Botswana, 2013; Molosiwa & Mangope, 2011). Hence, inclusive education has been certified as a basic human right since it helps all students to experience the same educational experiences. For this reason, it should be fully supported by all stakeholders (Jameson, et al., 2003).

Students with disabilities

Oliver (1996) identified students with learning disabilities as those who are physically and or mentally challenged, having low information retention abilities, and having difficulty in socialising skills. A study by Klimenko (2016), found out that the socialisation theory encouraged learners to establish peer relations regardless of their various backgrounds, and through this engagement only can they create inclusive environments. The study also established that through socialising, special needs learners develop high self-esteem and sense of belonging. However, some studies established that learners with special needs are sometimes frustrated by their learning disabilities which over time lead to negative feelings of self-worth and low confidence (Klimenko, 2016; Trampler, 2012). In tempting to address these challenges, Picard (2015) emphasised that in order to create an inclusive classroom where all students are respected, it is important to use strategies which prioritises the learners over their learning disability.

Implementing inclusive education

Morina (2017) maintained that the implementation of inclusive education within higher education can be challenging because it was originally developed for younger learners prior to its application within higher institutions of learning. Ultimately, as more learners with disabilities successfully completed their early schooling, the need to move towards inclusive practices within higher education has increased. Thus, many

countries have moved towards the implementation of inclusive education, primarily to manage the challenges faced by students with disabilities at tertiary education. In his study, Rieser (2016) pointed out that 148 countries have adopted the United Nation convention on persons with disability for integration into their mainstream education systems.

Challenges of inclusive education implementation in different parts of the world

Morgado (2016) emphasised that there are many challenges encountered during the implementation of inclusive education in Europe. Similarly, Roger (2013) argued that inclusive education suffers from collective indifference because of lack of resources and inconsistent practices, especially in impoverished communities. Furthermore, inclusive best practices in education are hindered by lack of well trained teachers and cultural beliefs and practices which prevent girls from exercising their right to education. Moreover, the kind of thinking about inclusive education held by people as translated into their discursive practices and actions also impede clear realisation of inclusive education; rendering subtle forms of exclusion instead.

Adedoyin & Okere (2017) established the lack of instructional materials and human capital as leading challenges in the implementation of inclusive education. In addition, a study conducted by Milinga (2013) found out that inadequate and poor physical, teaching and learning resources negatively affected the execution of inclusive education strategies; the study also discovered that teachers in inclusive education schools lacked the necessary skills to handle the special needs education curriculum. The socio-economic and the cultural variables were found to be common factors that affected teaching and learning in inclusive schools (Milinga, 2013).

Research identified some challenges of inclusive education in Europe such as; inadequate trained teachers, insufficient teaching and learning materials, negative attitudes towards learners with disabilities, as well as poor infrastructure; all these have made the learning of students with disabilities challenging (Watkins, 2007). On the other hand, India is cited amongst other countries to be effectively implementing inclusive education despite the various challenges faced during the implementation process (Singh, 2016). The various inclusive education challenges were established by different studies and these are discussed as follows:

a) The skills of teachers:

Research reveals that in India, teachers involved in inclusive education were not skilled to the desired standard with the competence relevant to inclusive education (Sanjeev, 2007). 70% of the regular school teachers had neither received training in special education nor had any experience teaching students with disabilities. Moreover, 87% of the teachers did not have access to inclusive education support services in their classrooms (Singh 2016).

b) Attitudes towards inclusive educations:

In addition to many other requirements, the implementation of inclusive education hugely requires positive attitudes towards inclusion and disability amongst teachers, parents, peers, administrators and policy planners (Doménech & Moliner, 2014). In many cases, negative attitudes still persist and this had adversely affected inclusive education endeavours in India. Research reveals that some teachers without qualifications in special education lacked confidence towards the students with learning disabilities when compared to teachers who have qualifications in special education (Leyser & Kirk, 2004). Literature further indicates that teachers with negative attitudes believe that the concept of inclusion is a burden to them since they had less to little experience on the subject matter. A similar study by Doménech and Moliner (2014) established that general education teachers did not support inclusion. Duhaney and Salend (2000) also discovered that many teachers who teach in normal schools indicated that they were not interested in teaching special education learners. These results therefore showed that teachers had negative attitudes towards the inclusion of students with disabilities into regular education classrooms as also supported by (Leyser & Kirk, 2004).

c) **Lack of awareness about children with disabilities among general teachers:**

The conventional teachers, at all levels, lack basic awareness about children with disabilities. They have their own socially and culturally constructed notions about certain obvious disabilities but lack the scientific and educational knowledge about the different learning disabilities portrayed by each learner such as: classification, labelling, special needs and adaptations (Frederickson, Dunsmuir, Lang & Monsen, 2004).

d) **improper curriculum adaptation:**

In order to practise inclusive education, curricular adaptation which is suited to special and unique needs of every learner, including children with disabilities, is crucial. Therefore, some concepts like 'Universal Instructional Design' are to be properly developed and incorporated into the curriculum. However, the necessary curricular adaptation to support inclusive education in India is either missing altogether or improper (Singh, 2016).

e) **The school environment and the difficulties in physical access:**

The school environment needs to be looked into and be accommodative when inclusive education is implemented. But it is indicated that such accommodations do not exist in the majority of schools. Facilities like ramps, lifts, and directional cues are mostly not provided in schools which offer inclusive education thus creating more challenges (Singh, 2016; Sanjeev, 2007).

f) **The support services:**

During the implementation of inclusive education in all educational institutions, at all levels, there is need for robust support services whose strength should both be quantitative and qualitative. However, the existing support services in Indian high education institutions are scarce, inadequate and sub-standard, Singh (2016) asserted.

g) **Family collaboration:**

Singh (2016) pointed out that it is essential to keep in mind the nature of the Indian society and culture since one's family has a very important role towards implementing inclusive education in India: it is significant not to overlook the country's customs. Family is considered to have the sole responsibility over their children and how they learn at school. Hence, inclusion can only be realised by motivating and involving family in the process (Lowenbraun, Madge & Affleck, 1990).

h) **Insufficient and improper pre-service teacher education:**

According to Frederickson et al. (2004), the pre-service teacher education programmes that are provided in the country fail to sensitise and equip the prospective teachers on inclusive educational practices, thus some modifications are required in order for education programmes to be more efficient. Presently, the education programmes that produce special education teachers are controlled by the Rehabilitation Council of India whereas the one who produce general teachers are managed by the National Council for Teacher Education (Singh, 2016; Newnham, 2009). These two apex bodies as highlighted by Frederickson et al. (2004) need to collaborate and devise some measures in order to produce skilful teachers who are capable of implementing inclusive education. The negative self-perceptions of children with disabilities pose a great challenge in the successful implementation of inclusive education (Singh, 2016).

i) **Improper policy planning and poor implementation**

The government of India as stated by Singh (2016) claims that it has implemented inclusive education nationwide and at all levels. However, the policy planning has been reported to be improper and some measures to assess the degree of implementation have not been developed. Besides, the implementation of inclusive education in the private sector has not yet been enforced and ensured (Singh, 2016).

Inclusive education in Botswana

The government of Botswana has made great efforts in infusing inclusive education at least in some of the government schools. These efforts have been adopted through the implementation of various Acts and strategies such as The Botswana Children's Act (2009), The Botswana Federation of Trade Unions (2007) and NDPs 8

and 9. The Botswana Children's Act (2009) promotes the notion that every child has the right to free basic education irrespective of their background. This Act empathises that the Botswana government need to ensure that all citizens have equal opportunity to education. On the other hand, the Botswana Federation of Trade Unions (2007) also stipulates that education for people with disabilities has to be given maximum attention: As a result of this, some notable achievements were establishment when additional Special Education Units were implemented by some of the tertiary education institutions around the country.

In addition, the Botswana government through the Ministry of Basic Education (MOBE) developed an Inclusive Education Policy which supports the implementation of inclusive education at early childhood and primary levels of education (World Health Organisation, 1996). The policy construes inclusive education as an educational approach that meets the needs of all learners despite their various learning abilities such as: health, gender and any other circumstances. But what is important about the successful implementation of inclusive education in schools, is the level at which stakeholders cooperate and strategize to support the concept of inclusivity in education (The Revised national policy on education, 1994). Amid the efforts of the government of Botswana towards supporting inclusive education, it is revealed that students with disabilities continue to face some challenges during their learning process in different parts of the country. In his study, Mangope (2017) noted that the government of Botswana identifies inclusive education as an essential component of any education system regardless of the various challenges experienced in its implementation.

Summary of Literature Reviewed

The reviewed literature indicated that the lack of teaching and learning resources are some of the many factors that impede the successful implementation of inclusive education in schools across Botswana, and other countries. Different researchers have different findings on the subject based on each country, and most of the findings clearly show that there are many challenges that need to be addressed. In addition, some researchers found out that ineffective inclusive education is a result of negative attitudes displayed by learners without learning disabilities and some teachers towards the special needs learners. To overcome these challenges, this study noted that tertiary institutions have a significant role to play towards the successful implementation of inclusive education in the context of Botswana. It was further established by this study that Inclusive Education has been perceived as a noble initiative that is essential to every country towards the creation of knowledge based economies; therefore, many countries across the globe continue to make efforts in the direction of implementing inclusive education in their education systems supported through polices; strategies and educational laws.

Methodology

A case study strategy was used in this study because it helped the researchers to focus on the specific cases, that is; the challenges faced by one private institution located in the Southern East region of Botswana towards supporting inclusive education strategies. According to Mills (2009), a case study is a qualitative research approach in which researchers focus on a unit of study known as a bounded system; it enables the researchers to closely examine the data within a specific context. The case study approach assisted the researchers to deliberately isolate a small study group (special needs students) that the research focused on. Moreover, the case study allowed the researchers to explore research participants' in their natural learning environment, and this contributed to the credibility and accuracy of the data collected.

Population

The population of this study comprised of students with physical and other types of disabilities as well as the lecturers in one of the tertiary institutions in the Southern East region of Botswana. The institution under study had 2 support staff under the special needs unit, and a total of 57 students with various special needs at the time of data collection. As such, the targeted population comprised of 30 students, 2 support staff and 7 lecturers thereby making a total of 39 participants.

Sampling

This study used purposive sampling to select 68% (30/57) of learners' with special learning needs; 100% (2/2) of support staff and 10% comprised of lecturers who at some point had taught special needs students who were registered to different programmes under different faculties at the time of data collection. The sample rates enabled the researchers to obtain sufficient data from the relevant participants who were actually affected by the implementation of inclusive education.

Data Collection procedure

- **Document analysis:** The study collected secondary data through the document analysis approach. Document analysis allowed the researchers to understand findings and existing knowledge on the subject. Moreover, the method enabled the researchers to recognise some gaps from the available policies. Furthermore, document analysis allowed the researchers to assess the levels of change and continuity of the phenomenon being investigated.
- **Interviews:** Semi-structured, in-depth interviews were conducted to explore the challenges faced by students with disabilities in their everyday learning activities. Students, support staff and lecturers were interviewed; the researchers led and conducted the interviews. The semi-structured interview questions used allowed the participants to respond in ways that were suitable to them, thus providing their perceptions and experiences effectively.
- **Focus groups:** This study also used (6) focus groups formed from 30 sampled students grouped according to their disabilities. Each focus group comprised of 5 participants both males and females; purposive sampling was conducted reflective of the learning abilities of participants. The researchers observed and guided the discussions amongst the peer groups. Discussions were instructed in English because all participants could communicate in the English language.
- **Observation method:** The researchers observed the challenges which affected the learners with disabilities during teaching and learning at the special needs unit; the observations were conducted in classes, and at the special needs department where the students did most of their continuous assessments. During the observations, observation sheets were recorded. The researchers had factors and guidelines written on the observation sheet and ticked per the observation guide and the activity took (20) minutes to complete per session. The sheet consisted of different challenges that affected the special needs students which were observed during the exercise. Hoque (2015) posited that during observations, one should observe and listen very carefully based on specific objectives guiding the study, a strategy which was implemented successfully in this study.

Findings and Discussion

The various studies conducted in Botswana on inclusive education revealed that the tertiary institutions which have incorporated inclusive education in their curriculum are faced with many challenges which involve: the lack of trained lecturers on inclusive education; limited teaching and learning resources; and shortage of proper infrastructure. These are some of the main factors that hindered the implementation of effective and efficient inclusive education. The respondents asserted that the negative attitudes held by lecturers have an impact towards the failure of successful inclusive education implementation; these findings imply that the lack of inclusive education expertise by lecturers play a significant role in the successful integration of inclusive education. With respect to the perceptions of lecturers towards inclusive education, it was revealed that lecturers encountered various obstacles when educating students with learning disabilities in their classrooms, therefore, It is evident from the experiences of students with disabilities that their learning experiences are presented with challenges which negatively affect their academic journey.

This study also established that buildings in the institution from which data were collected were initially not constructed to cater for learners with learning disabilities. The institution did not have ramps and corridors to facilitate easier movement of students who used wheelchairs. Thus, this made it difficult for disabled students to

move around classes as did other learners. On the other hand, lecturers pointed out that there were limited resources in the institution, especially for students with special needs. Most of the focus group discussants suggested the need for lecturers to be trained on inclusive education and that lecturers should be provided with up-to-date information on their curriculum arrangements. The findings from observations, focus groups and in-depth interviews indicated that the attitude of lecturers and some students hindered the successful provision of inclusive education. Based on the findings of this study, it is evident that both learners without learning disabilities and lecturers need to be trained on how to accept, tolerate and assist learners with disabilities in order to eliminate discrimination and stigma towards students with various learning abilities.

Conclusion

The findings of this study established that the education sector still has a lot of work to do towards making sure that the country implements a successful inclusive education strategy. These findings are anticipated to significantly contribute towards the development of a comprehensive and inclusive education curriculum policy that seeks to amend the current policies which are limited in addressing issues of inclusive education. The study suggests that there must be regular evaluation of tertiary institutions providing inclusive education as a way to enforce and implement inclusive education policies. Moreover, the Ministry of Higher Education should ensure that tertiary institutions have adequate teaching and learning resources to cater for special needs students. Tertiary institutions' managers, administrators and leaders should hire qualified and induct them intensively on inclusive education fostered to support inclusivity at all levels.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- Education institutions should provide training to lecturers and students on special education fostered to support inclusivity at all levels.
- Lecturers and the community at large should be encouraged to appreciate and take part in supporting inclusive education, and develop positive attitudes towards students with learning disabilities.
- The inclusive education institutions need to provide adequate teaching and learning resources as well conducive infrastructure in order to implement successful inclusive education.
- Education regulatory bodies need to ensure that education institutions fully support inclusive education at all levels integrated in curriculum, psycho-social support and academic support.

References

- i. Abery, B., Kincade, L., & Tichá, R. (2017). *Moving toward an Inclusive Education System*. Retrieved from: http://soced.cz/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/STUDY_SocEd_T5-1-2017-4-1.pdf
- ii. Adedoyin, O. & Okere. E. (2017). *The Significance of Inclusion Concept in the Educational System as Perceived by Junior Secondary School Teachers: Implications for Teacher Training Programmes in Botswana*. Retrieved from: [http://onlinesciencepublishing.com/assets/journal/ JOU0015/ ART 00164/ 1493113475_GJSSS-2017-3\(1\)-13-28.pdf](http://onlinesciencepublishing.com/assets/journal/ JOU0015/ ART 00164/ 1493113475_GJSSS-2017-3(1)-13-28.pdf)
- iii. Affleck, J., Lowenbraun, S., & Madge, S. (1990). *Parental satisfaction with integrated class placement of special education and general education students: Remedial and Special Education, 11 (4), 37-40*.
- iv. Ainscow, M. (2004). *Developing inclusive education systems: what are the levers for change?* Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/44838506_Developing_inclusive_education_systems_What_are_the_levers_for_change
- v. Doménech, A., & Moliner, O. (2014). *Families Beliefs about Inclusive Education Model: Social and Behavioural Sciences, 116 (1), 3286 -3291*.
- vi. Duhaney, L. M., & Salend, S. J. (2000). *Parental perceptions of inclusive educational placements: Remedial and Special Education, 21(2), 121-128*.

- vii. Dunsmuir, S., Frederickson, N., Lang, J., & Monsen, J. (2004). *Mainstream-special school inclusion partnerships: Pupil, parent and teacher perspectives*. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 8(1), 37-57.
- viii. Ford, J. (2003). *Educating students with learning disabilities in inclusive classrooms*, 2(3).
- ix. Government of Botswana, (2013). *National report on the development of education: "Inclusive education: The way of the future"*. Gaborone: Government Printers.
- x. Hoque, K. (2015). *Observation method*. Retrieved from: <https://www.slideshare.net/KhanHoque/observation-method-50894347>
- xi. Jameson, M., Johnson, J., McDonnell, J., Riesen, T., & Polychronis, S. (2003). *A comparison of constant time delay and simultaneous prompting within embedded instruction in general education classes with students with moderate to severe disabilities*: *Journal of Behaviour Education*, 12(4), 241-259
- xii. Jonas, O. (2014). *The right to inclusive education in Botswana: Present challenges and future prospects*. Retrieved from: <http://www.saflii.org/za/journals/ADRY/2014/1.html#pgfId-1069137>
- xiii. Jori, C. (2016). *A conceptual and legal framework for inclusive education* : Retrieved from: <https://inclusiveeducation.ca/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2017/03/legal-framework-inclusive-education>
- xiv. Milinga, J. R. (2013). *Educating Students with Disabilities in Inclusive Schools*
- xv. Klimenko, M. (2016). *Socialization of students with disabilities in an inclusive educational environment*: Retrieved from: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1115873.pdf>
- xvi. Kirk, R., & Leyser, Y. (2004). *Evaluating inclusion: An examination of parent views and factors influencing their perspectives*. *International Journal of Disability, Development and Education*, 51(3), 271- 285.
- xvii. Mangope, B. (2017). *Inclusive practices for learners with intellectual disabilities in primary schools in Botswana: What are teachers doing to enhance inclusion?* *Mosenodi Journal of the Botswana Educational Research Association*, 20(1), 32- 47.
- xviii. Materechera, E. K. (2018). *Inclusive education: why it poses a dilemma to some teachers*, *International Journal of Inclusive Education*. Retrieved from: DOI: 10.1080/13603116.2018.1492640
- xix. Mastropieri, M., & Scruggs, T. (2010). *The inclusive classroom: Strategies for effective instruction*. (4th Ed). Upper Saddle River: Prentice Hall, Inc.
- xx. McLeod, S. (2018). *Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs*: Retrieved from: <https://www.simplypsychology.org/maslow.html>
- xxi. Molosiwa, S. & Mangope, B. (2011). *Inclusive education of learners with intellectual disabilities in Botswana primary schools: Is it happening?* *International Association of Special Education*, 12(1), 54-57.
- xxii. Morgado, B. (2016). *Inclusive education in higher education*. Retrieved from: <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1111/1471-3802.12323>
- xxiii. Morina, A. (2017). *Inclusive education in higher education: challenges and opportunities* : Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/311892761_Inclusive_education_in_higher_education_challenges
- xxiv. Mukhopadhyay, S., Nenty, J., & Okechukwu, A. (2012). *Inclusive Education for Learners with Disabilities in Botswana Primary Schools*. Sage Open.
- xxv. Mpfu, E. (2007). *Inclusive Education in Zimbabwe: Policy, Curriculum, Practice, Family, and Teacher Education Issues*: *International Focus Issue*, 83(6), 342-346.
- xxvi. Nicole, K. (2018). *How to Overcome the Challenges to Inclusion* Retrieved from: <http://www.theinclusiveclass.com/2018/03/how-to-overcome-challenges-to-inclusion.htm>
- xxvii. Nestbit, F. (2015). *5 Ways To Build School Community*: Retrieved from: <https://www.ptotoday.com/ptotoday-articles/article/5949-5-ways-to-build-school-community>
- xxviii. Newnham, D. (2009). *Implementing inclusive education in schools*: Retrieved from: <http://www.cedol.org/wp-content/uploads/2012/02/63-65-2009.pdf>

- xxix. *Obiozor, D. (2010). Academic and social challenges facing students with developmental and learning disabilities in higher institutions: implications to African colleges and universities. Retrieved from: Jeff/downloads/1585-article%20text-8724-1-10-.*
- xxx. *Oliver, M. (1996). Understanding disability. Basingstoke: Macmillan.*
- xxxi. *Olufemi, A, S. (2015). Determinants of Successful Inclusive Education Practice in Lagos State Nigeria . Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1158470.pdf>.*
- xxxii. *Open Society Foundation. (2019).The value of inclusive education: Retrieved from [https://www. open societyfoundations.org/explainers/value-inclusive-education](https://www.open societyfoundations.org/explainers/value-inclusive-education)*
- xxxiii. *Picard, D. (2015). Teaching Students with Disabilities: Retrieved from: <https guides-sub-pages/disabilities/>*
- xxxiv. *Republic of Botswana. (1994). The Revised national policy on education, 1994. Retrieved from: <https://planipolis.iiep.unesco.org/en/1994/revised-national-policy-education-5274>*
- xxxv. *Rieser, P. (2017) Progress to Inclusive Education in South East Asia: What are the issues?: Retrieved from <http://worldofinclusion.com/progress-to-inclusive-education-in-south-east-asia-what-are-the-issues/>*
- xxxvi. *Roger, S. (2013) Meeting Some Challenges of Inclusive Education in an Age of Exclusion: Asian Journal of Inclusive Education Vol. 1, No. 2, July 2013, 3-1.*
- xxxvii. *Singh, J. (2016). Inclusive Education in India: Concept, Need and Challenges. SRJIS Bimonthly, 3, 3222.*
- xxxviii. *Sanjeev, K. (2007). Inclusive Education in India, Electoral Journal on Inclusive education, 7(2).*
- xxxix. *Save the Children Report. (2016). Inclusive education: what, why and how. Retrieved from: <https://www.savethechildren.it/sites/default/files/files/uploads/pubblicazioni/inclusive-education-what-why-and-how.pdf>.*
- xl. *The African Disability Rights. (2015). The right to inclusive education in Botswana: Present challenges and future prospects (Chapter 1) [2014] ADRY. Retrieved from <http://www.saflii.org/za/journals/ADRY/2014/1.html#pgfId-1069521>.*
- xli. *The Botswana Federation of Trade Unions. (2007). Policy of Education in Botswana: Retrieved from <library.fes.de/pdf-files/bueros/Botswana/04922.pdf07>.*
- xlii. *The National Academies Press. (2019). The Diversity of Students with Disabilities: Retrieved from: <https://www.nap. edu/read/5788/chapter/5#69>.*
- xliii. *Trampler, F. (2012). Inclusion Classrooms as it Relates to Self-Esteem, Behaviour, and Social Skills: Retrieved from: <https://firescholars.seu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1025&context=honors>*
- xliv. *UNESCO. (2019). Inclusive education. Retrieved from: <https://en.unesco.org/themes/inclusion-in-education/>*
- xlv. *UNICEF. (1998). The Education of Children with Special Needs: Barriers and Opportunities in Central and Eastern Europe. Retrieved from: <https://www.unicef-irc.org/publications/pdf/eps67.pdf>*
- xlvi. *Watkins, A. (2007). Assessment in Inclusive Settings: Key issues for policy and practice, Odense: European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education.*
- xlvii. *World Health Organisation (1996). National Policy on Care for People with Disabilities. Retrieved from: <https://www.mindbank.info/item/2134>*